

Familial catalysts: How parental involvement relates to the comprehension level of the primary grade learners

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Abstract

This quantitative study investigated the influence of parental involvement on the reading comprehension of 106 primary grade learners (Grades 2-3) at Bagbaguin Elementary School in Bagbaguin, Pandi, Bulacan, Philippines. Employing a descriptive regression design, the research utilized a survey adapted from a research study to assess four dimensions of parental involvement: encouragement, reading activities, providing materials, and educational support. Learners' reading comprehension levels were measured using existing Modified Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (MCRLA) scores.

Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that reading activities were the strongest predictor of reading comprehension. This highlights the significant positive impact of parents actively engaging in reading with their children and fostering a home reading culture. The findings underscore the crucial role of direct parental involvement in reading-related activities for improving primary grade learners' reading comprehension. These results suggest that educational interventions should prioritize empowering parents to engage in meaningful reading activities with their children and ensuring access to diverse reading materials at home.

Keywords: Parental Involvement; Reading Comprehension Level; MCRLA Scores; Regression Analysis; Reading-Related Activities; Primary Grade Learners

1. Introduction

Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill that enables individuals to understand, interpret, and apply information from written texts. It involves recognizing words, grasping meanings, identifying key ideas, and making inferences [1]. More formally, reading comprehension has been defined as "the ability to define word by word and create a profound idea out of the talks given or read." A person may know how to read certain words, but Comprehension is something that is developed, practiced, learned, and experienced over time [2]. Reading serves as the foundation of all learning, making strong reading skills essential for academic success. Through reading, individuals can develop lifelong learning and essential survival skills, which contribute to personal growth, competence, and future achievements. These skills, in turn, help shape individuals into competitive members of society [3].

A child's parents are undeniably essential to their lives. It is not limited to survival and financial assistance alone. Parenting mostly requires physical, emotional, and educational assistance. It is indisputable that every parent frets about how well their children are performing academically [4]. It is widely accepted that parents have a significant role in their children's education and influence their learning and development [5]. Good reading comprehension cannot be

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acquired if parents are not responsible for assessing their children's learning. Parental involvement must be met to maintain the proper academic performance of a learner.

The primary grades at the elementary level are a critical period for literacy development. During this period, it is imperative to cultivate the habit of reading to ensure long-term academic success [6]. A problem that most learners, especially in the primary levels of elementary school, face is the difficulty of reading and comprehending texts. One factor that contributes to that problem is the occurrence of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID 19) pandemic. The global pandemic outbreak has forced school closures to prevent the transmission of the coronavirus; this heavily disrupted children's learning experiences, leading to setbacks in reading skills [7].

Individuals who lack this vital ability are frequently economically and socially disadvantaged. There are 774 million people worldwide who are illiterate, according to the 86% global literacy rate. Among the most significant societal issues of our day is illiteracy. Millions of kids and teens struggle with reading or don't know how to read. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) 2018 estimate, 258 million children lack literacy. One out of four children in underdeveloped countries are illiterate [8].

The reading literacy test administered by Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) evaluates a person's ability to comprehend, apply, think critically about, and interact with written materials. The article critically examines and evaluates the present trends in reading performance across the Asia-Pacific regions and nations, taking into account the findings of the most recent PISA cycle. To further demonstrate how certain factors influence a nation's reading literacy performance, comparisons between high-performing nations (e.g., Singapore) and low-performing nations (e.g., Philippines) are made [9].

According to the PISA 2018 result, it was revealed that the Philippines was ranked lowest among the 79 participating countries in reading comprehension. Meanwhile, in the 2022 result, the Philippines was ranked 76th out of the 81 countries in reading comprehension. In overall ranked scores in reading comprehension, mathematics, and science the Philippines is ranked at the bottom 10 over the 81 countries that show minimal improvement of the learners [10]. The dismal performance of the Philippines in the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) sends the message that the country's educational system needs to take reading instruction seriously [11].

Recent studies have shown an inconsistent influence between parental involvement and learners' academic achievement, yielding varied results. Maimad et al. [12] conducted a 2023 study to analyze how parental involvement affects student academic results in the Philippines through the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) which operates as a conditional cash transfer program. The research showed no statistical relationship between parental involvement and student academic success because parents showed minimal participation in home learning activities and school decision-making and volunteering yet learners achieved high grades in core subjects. The 2024 study by Rahman et al. [13] analyzed how socioeconomic status (SES) affects the relationship between parental involvement and reading comprehension skills of learners. The research established that parental support enhanced reading development equally across all socioeconomic status groups yet the effect size proved stronger in families with higher incomes. The differences in these results were mainly due to parental education levels and the availability of home resources. The research indicates that parental involvement affects academic achievement differently based on the particular involvement activities and environmental conditions. The research demonstrates the necessity to conduct additional studies about how different parental involvement methods affect student learning results.

The researchers are investigating the effects of parental involvement on young learners' reading comprehension at Bagbaguin Elementary School. This study aims to demonstrate how active parental involvement in reading instruction can result in notable gains for kids' reading abilities as well as for their general academic achievement. This study intends to find practical ways to promote greater parental involvement by looking at how parents engage in their kids' education. The results may help educators, parents, and school administrators build a more encouraging learning environment and improve learners' reading skills. After all, a solid foundation in reading is essential for future academic and non-academic success.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The general problem of the study is: "How Parental Involvement Relates to the Reading Comprehension Level of the Primary Grade Learners?"

Specifically, this study will seek answers to the following questions:

What is the level of parental involvement in reading activities among the respondents, in terms of:

- Encouragement and Motivation;
- Reading Activities;
- Providing Materials; and
- Educational Support?

What is the level of reading comprehension of the learners based on the Modified Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (MCRLA) Scores?

Is there a significant influence of parental involvement on reading comprehension among primary grade learners?

What parental involvement activities may be proposed to help the primary grade learners in their reading comprehension?

1.2. Hypothesis of the Study

- **Ho1.** There is no significant influence between encouragement and motivation involvement of the parents and the reading comprehension level of the primary grade learners.
- **Ho2.** There is no significant influence between reading activities involvement of the parents and the reading comprehension level of the primary grade learners.
- **Ho3.** There is no significant influence between providing materials to the learners and the reading comprehension level of the primary grade learners.
- **Ho4.** There is no significant influence between the educational support from parents and the reading comprehension level of the primary grade learners.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

This research employs a quantitative research approach utilizing a descriptive regression research design. A descriptive regression research design uses regression analysis, a statistical method, to explore the influence between variables and make predictions. It is a descriptive approach, meaning it focuses on characterizing the influences between variables rather than establishing causal relationships. The research design aims to examine the influence of parental involvement on the reading comprehension levels of primary grade learners. The sample size is determined based on the total number of Grade 2 and 3 learners in Bagbaguin Elementary School.

A survey questionnaire was used to collect data from parents regarding their level of involvement in their children's reading. The questionnaires consisted of likert scale questions that allow for a structured analysis of parental involvement. Additionally, the most recent results of the Modified Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (mCRLA) were used to measure the reading comprehension levels of the primary grade learners.

2.2. Participants

The researchers of this study selected the participating Grade 2 and 3 primary grade learners in Bagbaguin Elementary School of Bagbaguin, Pandi, Bulacan which consists of two (2) sections each in the School Year 2024-2025.

The respondents of this study were the parents of all Grade 2 and Grade 3 learners enrolled at Bagbaguin Elementary School. The study population consisted of 54 parents of the Grade 2 learners and 52 parents of the Grade 3 learners, resulting in a total of 106 potential respondents.

2.3. Instruments

The researchers adapted a questionnaire from a study Developing a Questionnaire for Assessing Parental Involvement in Reading in Sultanate of Oman in International Journal of Language and Linguistics, Vol. 6, No 1, March 2019 [14]. The aim of the study was to develop a reliable and valid instrument to assess the parents' involvement in reading. This study tries to help the Ministry of Education in the Sultanate of Oman by providing a good instrument to assess Omani parents' involvement in reading with their children which is considered a vital aspect of language development. The alpha

coefficients for this questionnaire ranged from .85 to .92, thus the questionnaire is ready for implementation. The researchers modified it to fit necessarily for the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by three experts: two Doctors of Philosophy, majoring in Filipino, and a Master Teacher, majoring in English. The questionnaire served as the primary tool for the researchers to address the research problem.

The questionnaire consists of two parts. Part I gathered the parent's sociodemographic profile, such as their name, age, relationship to the learner, educational attainment, family status, number of family members, and household income. Part II included a 5-point Likert Scale questionnaire designed to assess parental involvement, specifically focusing on how parents involve themselves with their children in reading activities with four (4) themes, which are Encouragement and Motivation, Reading Activities, Providing Materials, and Educational Support. These questions aimed to determine if there is a significant influence between parental involvement and the reading comprehension levels of the learners.

2.4. Procedure

To conduct the current study, the researchers constructed a formal letter addressed to the school principal, requesting permission to conduct the survey. A similar letter was sent in advance to each participant, specifically the parents of 106 Grade 2 and Grade 3 learners at the school. Participants were given time to respond, after which the completed survey questionnaires were collected.

The researchers used the survey method under their supervision. The objective of this study is to explore how parental involvement can improve learners' reading comprehension level, potentially enhancing their overall academic performance in the future. After collecting the responses, the researchers tallied the data for analysis and consulted a statistician to determine the appropriate statistical tools.

3. Results and discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the gathered data using the research instruments designed to assess parental involvement and reading comprehension levels of primary grade learners. There are different tables presented in this chapter that are based on the statement of the problem presented in Chapter I.

3.1. Level of Parental Involvement of the Parents in Reading Activities

The table includes questionnaires that covered the level of Parental Involvement among Primary Grade Learners through four (4) themes mainly: Encouragement and Motivation, Reading Activities, Providing Materials, and Educational Support.

3.1.1. Encouragement and Motivation

Table 1 Distribution of Data Gathered from the Parents in terms of Encouragement and Motivation

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I encourage my children to read the words of God, daily.	4.08	1.03	Often	Often Observed
2. I encourage my children to read about social and religious events.	3.92	1.18	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
3. I encourage my children to read road signs and shop notices.	4.26	0.95	Often	Often Observed
4. I allow my children to choose educational books that they like to read.	4.25	0.96	Often	Often Observed
5. I encourage my child to ask questions and discuss stories after reading.	4.26	1.01	Often	Often Observed
OVERALL	4.16	0.09	Often	Often Observed

The table 1 presents the five list practices of a parent and its interpretation under the terms of encouragement and motivation. The finding shows that the two most highly rated practices are "I encourage my children to read road signs and shop notices" and "I encourage my child to ask questions and discuss stories after reading." got a rated score of 4.26

and both interpreted as often observed, these results demonstrate how eager parents are to allow their kids to participate in real-world reading situations and encourage critical thinking through conversation. The "I allow my children to choose educational books that they like to read." was the second rated score of 4.25 and followed by "I encourage my children to read the words of God, daily." that got a rate of 4.08 and both were interpreted as often observed. While the "I encourage my children to read about social and religious events." got the lowest rate of 3.92 but still got interpreted as sometimes observed, this indicates that, despite receiving the lowest rating, parents still often encourage their kids to read about religious and social events and suggests that these practices are still a part of developing a comprehensive reading habit.

Three related studies regarding parental involvement and motivating their child's reading supported these findings. According to Gino [15], parents who actively engaged in reading-related activities at home such as reading aloud to their children, providing them with books, and creating an environment that encouraged reading strongly benefited their reading development. He believes that parental assistance can help children develop a love of reading and improve their comprehension abilities. Similarly, according to The Annie E. Casey Foundation [16], parental involvement in their children's activities is essential, particularly when it comes to reading at home. If parents are supportive and willing to help with their children's needs, the student gains confidence and is motivated to read and study. In line with this, Budao [17] stated that by having reading sessions at home with their parents, children can be inspired to set aside time for reading. It is also important to encourage leisure reading that will strengthen learners' appreciation of reading and highlight its advantages for their academic work and other extracurricular activities.

To sum up, these findings show that some of the respondents foster encouragement and motivation in order to enhance their child's reading comprehension. Fostering a love of reading in children and facilitating regular reading sessions with parents might improve their academic performance and involvement in extracurricular activities.

3.1.2. Reading Activities

Table 2 Distribution of Data Gathered from the Parents in terms of Reading Activities

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
6. I share my interests in reading with my family.	3.75	1.26	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
7. I am involved in reading stories with my family.	3.68	1.24	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
8. I read some stories with my children at home.	3.77	1.21	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
9. I organize reading competition with family members	3.66	1.27	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
10. I discuss with my children about the books they read	4.13	1.06	Often	Often Observed
OVERALL	3.80	0.09	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed

Table 2 shows the family involvement in reading activities with the learners. The table has five statements presenting various reading activities within families, along with their average ratings indicating how often the activities are performed and the standard deviation showing the variation in how often they are performed. The statement "I discuss with my children about the books they read" has the highest average rating of (4.13), indicating that discussing books with children is a highly prioritized or frequently observed behavior in the data. The following statement "I organize reading competitions with family members" was the lowest-rated activity (3.66) which is still within the "sometimes" category, but suggests that organizing reading competitions might be a less common activity compared to other forms of family reading engagement. Most activities are rated in the "sometimes" range (3.66 to 4.13). This suggests that the participants generally engage in these reading-related activities frequently, which could imply a strong familial engagement with reading.

These findings align with Kuruppu [18], who found that parents focus more on language comprehension, like discussions and asking questions, rather than technical skills. The social, interactive nature of reading helped build strong reading habits. Similarity, Ahmad et al. [19] stated that most parents only engage in reading activities once a month, those who frequently participate in leisure reading, including book discussions, significantly enhance their children's academic success. Less structured activities like reading competitions were not commonly practiced. Supporting this, Labajo [20] emphasized a strong correlation between parental involvement and children's literacy development. It highlights how everyday support like reading with children and discussing content is more common and influential than formal academic interventions.

The findings of this study indicate that families are actively involved in their children's reading development, with most activities occurring frequently. The high rating for discussing books suggests that parents value interactive and meaningful conversations around reading, which plays a crucial role in fostering comprehension and interest.

3.1.3. Providing Materials

Table 3 Distribution of Data Gathered from the Parents in terms of Providing Materials

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
11. I invest in buying books.	3.67	1.25	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
12. I save money to ensure my child has access to new books.	3.75	1.23	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
13. I give my children books as a gift.	3.40	1.18	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
14. I provide my children with books and stories that they need.	3.91	1.14	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
15. I provide e-books for my children.	3.46	1.34	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
16. I search for resources on the internet for my child to read.	3.86	1.16	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
17. I take my children to libraries.	3.25	1.42	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
18. I take my children to bookshops.	3.53	1.40	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
19. I borrow story books from my friends' libraries.	3.20	1.44	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
OVERALL	3.56	0.12	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed

Table 3 illustrates the frequency of different actions taken by parents in supplying reading materials and resources for their children. These actions emphasize both conventional and digital methods of acquiring books, including buying, saving funds for books, offering e-books, and making trips to libraries or bookstores. This table presents nine statements. The statement 'I provide my children with the books and stories they need' (3.91) ranks the highest among parents supplying materials, indicating that prioritizing the provision of necessary reading resources is a common practice among parents. The next statement, 'I borrow storybooks from my friends' libraries' (3.20), falls into the rare category and holds the lowest average regarding parents supplying reading materials. This suggests that parents are taking the initiative to enhance their children's education by seeking out resources and platforms beyond what the school offers.

According to Project Appleseed [21], parents play a crucial role in fostering early reading comprehension by exposing their children to books, newspapers, and various printed materials in their environment. In addition, community-based family literacy programs should utilize local resources such as book fairs, author readings, and literacy workshops, which provide engaging educational opportunities for both parents and their children. Williams [22] suggests that educators can encourage parental involvement by promoting access to resources and maintaining open communication, thereby strengthening home-school collaborations that help support children's education effectively. Sheldon-Dean [23] assessed the impact of interactive e-books in comparison to traditional print books, standard educational programs, and non-interactive e-books. Even though a significant number of children's literature is now available in digital formats, it remains uncertain if e-books provide the same developmental advantages as print versions. Some research indicates that print books promote deeper and more meaningful interactions between parents and children, whereas digital reading might lead to quicker and less focused engagement. Nonetheless, e-books can be beneficial, particularly for families with limited access to physical books. They present a convenient option while traveling or in

settings with fewer resources. In conclusion, although parents often lean towards print books, there is a need for increased efforts in promoting library usage, book borrowing, and engagement with digital materials to aid in children's literacy growth.

3.1.4. Educational Support

Table 4 Distribution of Data Gathered from the Parents in terms of Educational Support

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
20. I advise my children to read the contents of products before buying them.	4.21	0.95	Often	Often Observed
21. I ask my children to read the prescriptions' drug.	3.89	1.12	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
22. I help my child with difficult words or concepts while reading.	4.25	0.99	Often	Often Observed
23. I monitor my child's reading progress by attending homeroom meetings.	3.91	1.20	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
24. I follow my children's reading performance in school.	4.10	1.21	Often	Often Observed
OVERALL	4.07	0.12	Often	Often Observed

Table 4 illustrates the various methods through which parents offer educational support to their children in Grades 2 and 3. This table includes five (5) statements. The statement "I help my child with difficult words or concepts while reading" achieved the highest mean score of 4.25, which is interpreted as Often Observed. The statement "I advise my children to read the contents of products before buying them" obtained a mean of 4.21, also classified as Often Observed. Following this is the statement "I follow my children's reading performance in school," which received a mean of 4.10 and is likewise interpreted as Often Observed. The statement "I monitor my child's reading progress by attending homeroom meetings" earned a mean score of 3.91, with the interpretation of "Sometimes Observed". To conclude, the phrase "I asked my children to read the prescription drug" received an average score of 3.89, which is categorized as Sometimes Observed. This indicates that the majority of parents with Grade 2 and 3 students assist their children in understanding challenging words or concepts during reading.

According to William [24], parents who read with their children regularly contribute significantly to the development of reading fluency and comprehension skills. This practice was particularly beneficial for younger students. Also, parents who provided academic support, especially with reading and writing tasks, saw improvements in their children's writing abilities and vocabulary. The responsibility to improve the children's performance should not always be entrusted to teachers; parents can also play their role well. According to Tigaronita and Tagaylo [25], parents and educators may collaborate to provide a supportive and consistent learning environment that develops the child's reading ability and promotes a love of reading. It is important to have communication between the parent and the teacher to know the child's shortcomings in school and what the parent needs to do for the child at home. According to Bardwell [26], the strategies for kids in grade 3 and above, authenticity matters. They need to find real value in the reading and writing activities they're engaging in. Also, if your kid is showing struggles with reading or writing, it's important to reach out, support them, and stay in close contact with their teacher. They may need additional and targeted support with developing certain skills. In this way, the parent will know the child's weaknesses and strengths with the help of a connection between the parent and teacher, which will result in the child's learning in literacy. Educational support greatly helps a child's learning, starting with guidance in reading, especially with difficult words that they will encounter in the books they read. This will benefit their academic performance, and they will develop a wide vocabulary through learning with the guidance of parents and teachers.

3.1.5. Summary of Level of Parental Involvement in Reading Activities of the Learners

The findings indicated a considerable degree of parental involvement in fostering reading comprehension among primary grade learners, as demonstrated by an average rating of 3.90, interpreted as sometimes observed. This level of parental involvement is captured in four primary themes: Encouragement and Motivation, Reading Activities, Providing Materials, and Educational Support.

Table 5 Summary of Distribution of Level of Parental Involvement

Indicators	Ave Rating	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Encouragement and Motivation	4.16	0.09	Often	Often Observed
2. Reading Activities	3.80	0.09	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
3. Providing Materials	3.56	0.12	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed
4. Educational Support	4.07	0.12	Often	Often Observed
OVERALL	3.90	0.02	Sometimes	Sometimes Observed

Encouragement and Motivation received the highest average rating of 4.16, implying that parents often observed offer emotional reinforcement, praise, and ongoing encouragement, which play a crucial role in building their learner's confidence and enthusiasm for reading. Reading Activities received an average rating of 3.80, indicating that parents sometimes observed engaging in reading with their children, whether it was reading aloud, telling stories, or discussing books. While this is sometimes observed, there's still room for even more active involvement to help improve comprehension. Providing Materials had the lowest rating of 3.56, yet it still falls within the category of sometimes observed. The findings indicate that while parents generally supply reading materials, there might be limitations regarding the variety or access to suitable and age-appropriate reading resources at home. Lastly, Educational Support has a solid average rating of 4.07, underscoring that parents often observed assisting their children with reading-related school assignments and keeping track of their academic progress, reinforcing the literacy skills taught in the classroom.

Parental involvement is vital for the academic progress of children, especially in literacy. Kuruppu [27] points out that parents who have a genuine passion for reading are likely to create more engaging and interactive reading experiences, which actively involve their children and foster their reading development. This influence is even stronger when parents are knowledgeable about early literacy, as it allows them to guide their children more effectively. Nonetheless, Ssenkasi [28] notes that while some parents do offer educational resources, there is still a significant inconsistency in this support, which adversely affects students' academic performance. This indicates that mere enthusiasm is inadequate—consistent engagement backed by resources is crucial. Supporting this notion, Deen [29] highlights that parents are the primary educators of their children, and their educational support significantly impacts not only academic success but also overall well-being. Collectively, these studies emphasize the need for parents to be consistently and actively engaged in their children's educational journeys, through both meaningful interactions and the provision of proper learning resources.

3.2. Reading Comprehension Level of the Learners

The table includes results of the Modified Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (mCRLA) scores among Primary Grade Learners through five (5) categories such as: Low Emerging Reader, High Emerging Reader, Developing Reader, Transitioning Reader, and Reading at Grade Level.

Table 6 Distribution of Data Gathered from MCRLA Scores of the Learners

MCRLA Scores	Frequency	Percentage
Low Emerging Reader	16	15.09%
High Emerging Reader	17	16.04%
Developing Reader	17	16.04%
Transitioning Reader	18	16.98%
Reading At Grade Level	38	35.85%
TOTAL	106	100.00%

The data indicates that 38 learners out of 106 are in the "Reading at Grade Level" category, which represents the largest percentage of all categories at 35.85%. This shows that these learners receive a good foundation support for their academic success at home. The "Transitioning Reader" category has 18 learners with 16.98%, while both "High

Emerging Reader" and "Developing Reader" categories have 17 learners each for 16.04%. Lastly, 16 learners fall into the "Low Emerging Reader" category, which represents the lowest percentage of all categories at 15.09%.

The data collected suggests that learners' reading proficiency and parental support are positively correlated. The fact that the majority of learners are proficient in reading at the grade level shows how parents who are involved and supportive can have a positive influence on their children's literacy development. The existence of learners in the lower categories, however, also highlights the necessity of further assistance, particularly for families whose children are still developing or emerging readers.

According to Assari et al, [30] while parental educational attainment may improve children's superior temporal cortical surface area, promoting reading ability, this effect may be unequal across racial/ethnic groups. They need to address societal barriers that diminish parental educational attainment's marginal returns for middle-class minority families. Social and public policies need to go beyond equal access and address structural and societal barriers that hinder middle-class families of color and their children. Building upon this, Xu and Fu [31] said that parental educational attainment significantly impacts children's academic performance. Complementing these findings, Havdahl et al, [32] conclude that parents' educational attainment, or a closely related trait, is likely to affect their children's test scores during school. In addition, the effects of fathers' educational attainment appear to be greater than mothers, and there is some evidence that these effects may indicate differences in parenting behaviour.

To sum up, increased educational levels of parents have a beneficial impact on their children's literacy growth and academic success, with these outcomes being influenced by psychological expectations and differing according to parental roles and broader systemic factors. It is crucial to tackle the structural obstacles that result in reduced benefits for minority families to guarantee that every child has the opportunity to gain equally from their parents' educational accomplishments.

3.3. Influence Between the Level of Parental involvement and Reading Comprehension Level of the Learners

The table includes regression analysis between level of parental involvement and reading comprehension level of the learners. The researchers used multiple linear regression calculator for this table.

Table 7 Regression Analysis Between Level of Parental Involvement and Reading Comprehension Level of the Learners

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig-value	Decision	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
Encouragement and Motivation	0.29	0.25	0.15	1.19	0.24	Don't Reject Ho1	Encouragement and motivation involvement of the parents is not affecting the reading comprehension.
Reading Activities	0.48	0.21	0.29	2.25	0.03	Reject Ho2	Reading activities involving the parents is affecting the reading comprehension.
Providing Materials	0.27	0.19	0.17	1.43	0.16	Don't Reject Ho3	Providing materials of the parents in reading is not affecting the reading comprehension.
Educational Support	-0.02	0.22	-0.01	-0.08	0.93	Don't Reject Ho4	Educational support of the parents in reading activities is not affecting the reading comprehension.
Dependent variable: Reading Comprehension							

Table 7 shows the regression analysis that examines the relationship between different facets of parental involvement and the reading comprehension level of learners. First, the coefficient for encouragement and motivation is 0.29, with a significance value (Sig-value) of 0.24. Since this p-value is greater than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis (Ho1). Therefore, the level of parental encouragement and motivation did not have a statistically significant effect on the reading comprehension levels of the learners. The interpretation provided in the table states that "Encouragement and motivation involvement of the parents is not affecting the reading comprehension."

Second, the coefficient for reading activities is 0.48, with a significance value (Sig-value) of 0.03. This p-value is less than 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis (Ho2). Therefore, the level of parental involvement in reading activities has a statistically significant positive effect on the reading comprehension levels of the learners. The positive coefficient suggests that higher levels of parental involvement in reading activities are associated with higher reading comprehension scores. The interpretation in the table states that "Reading activities involving the parents is affecting the reading comprehension."

Next, the coefficient for providing materials is 0.27, with a significance value (Sig-value) of 0.16. Since this p-value is greater than 0.05, the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis (Ho3). Therefore, the extent to which parents provide reading materials did not have a statistically significant effect on the reading comprehension levels of the learners. The table's interpretation, "Providing materials of the parents in reading is not affecting the reading comprehension," aligns with this finding.

Lastly, the coefficient for educational support is -0.02, with a significance value (Sig-value) of 0.93. Since this p-value is considerably greater than 0.05, the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis (Ho4). Therefore, the level of educational support provided by parents did not have a statistically significant effect on the reading comprehension levels of the learners. The interpretation provided, "Educational support of the parents in reading activities is not affecting the reading comprehension," is consistent with this result.

The regression analysis reveals that parental involvement in reading activities is the only statistically significant predictor of reading comprehension among the examined variables. This suggests that actively engaging in reading with children has a positive and significant impact on their reading comprehension level. The other facets of parental involvement, encouragement and motivation, providing materials, and educational support, did not show a statistically significant relationship with reading comprehension in this study. This does not necessarily mean these factors are unimportant, but rather that their influence was not statistically detectable within the parameters of this particular research, their potential influence should not be entirely dismissed and may warrant further investigation in future studies.

Furthermore, William et al. [33] state that parents who read with their children regularly contributed significantly to the development of reading fluency and comprehension skills. He concluded that this home reading practice activity was particularly beneficial for younger students. Kuruppu [34] highlights that joint book reading is a valuable home reading activity that supports the development of literacy skills and language comprehension. In addition, Caliskan and Ulas [35] state that parents' involvement in reading activities with their children is significant because it fosters a supportive learning environment that enhances children's literacy skills. Structured reading activities led by parents provide an experiential learning context that can effectively reinforce the skills taught in school, confirming the importance of collaborative efforts in education.

The results from a study of Szenczi, et al. [36] indicate that the motivational factors analyzed were not substantial influencers of the home literacy environment. The only motivational factor that showed a slight yet statistically significant influence on the variance in home literacy environment was performance goals in fourth grade, specifically students' aspiration for recognition and improved grades. The observation that students' own views regarding their reading motivation do not significantly impact the level of home reading support does not contradict prior research highlighting that parents can shape their children's reading support at home over time based on their perceptions of those children's motivation. As stated by Cañete [37], there is no considerable difference in the level of parental support and the reading abilities of Grade 3 students. This indicates that the range of resources provided by parents does not influence the reading skills of the students. Although a significant connection between parental involvement and reading competence is absent, it is advised that parents and teachers persist in collaborating to enhance the skills of the learners. Similarly, Derotas et al. [38] states that even though participants displayed a desire to read and received some educational support from their parents, these factors were not significantly linked to their reading comprehension abilities. This could be attributed to the limited time parents have due to their jobs and other work-related responsibilities. While they may have the intention to assist, their support might lack consistency or effectiveness. Many

parents are not trained in education, and even those who may find it challenging to dedicate time because of work pressures.

4. Conclusion

The study shows that different forms of parental involvement have varying levels of impact. The study reveals a significant relationship between parental involvement in reading activities and the reading comprehension levels of primary grade learners. Specifically, the research underscores that when parents actively engage in reading with their children, it has a positive and statistically significant impact on enhancing the children's reading comprehension abilities. This finding highlights the importance of shared reading experiences between parents and children. However, other dimensions of parental involvement, including encouragement and motivation, providing materials, and offering educational support, did not demonstrate the same level of significant influence on reading comprehension. While these aspects are undoubtedly valuable in a child's overall development, the study indicates that their direct impact on reading comprehension, as measured in this research, was not as pronounced as the impact of parents directly engaging in reading activities with their children. This suggests that the act of reading together, discussing texts, and engaging with the material collaboratively is particularly crucial for developing reading comprehension skills in primary grade learners.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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